

DESIGNING PEDAGOGICAL SUBJECTS. A DYNAMIC APPROACH TO TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract: As educators strive to create engaging and effective learning experiences, the Pedagogical Science Design Methodology offers a comforting approach. This methodology involves developing learning experiences that reflect the principles of design thinking, encouraging creativity, critical thinking, and student-centeredness. In this article, we will explore the main elements of this educational methodology and how it can enrich the learning process.

Key words: Learning objective, advantages and strengths, guidance, Design.

1. Empathy and understanding of learners. Designing pedagogic topics begins with creating empathy and understanding for learners. Educators must learn about the needs, motivations, and aspirations of their students, and tailor the learning experience to meet their unique needs. Through active listening and observation, educators gain insights into their students' learning styles, preferences, and strengths, enabling them to create meaningful and engaging learning.

2. Classification of learning goals and results. Specific learning objectives determine the desired results of the pedagogical subject. These goals serve as a guide for both learners and learners, helping to focus the teaching and learning process. By articulating these goals, learners can effectively align activities, assessments, and resources to ensure the desired learning outcomes are achieved.

3. Idea and innovative educational strategies. Design thinking principles encourage educators to be innovative and open-minded when developing instructional strategies. They are encouraged to actively engage with students, brainstorm and explore creative ideas that enable critical thinking and problem solving. This can include hands-on activities, project-based learning, collaborative group work, or integrating technology tools to enhance the learning experience.

4. Prototype and Iterate: Pedagogical science design involves an iterative process of prototyping and refining instructional strategies. Educators should provide facilities for testing and providing feedback to students on a variety of

learning activities. By gathering insights from students about what is working and what needs improvement, educators can improve instructional methods and materials, ensuring that the learning experience is optimized for student success.

5. Reflection and evaluation: Reflection is very important in the design of pedagogical subjects. Educators should provide opportunities for students to reflect on their learning experiences, self-assess, and receive feedback from both peers and teachers. Assessment methods should be varied, focusing not only on traditional tests but also on projects, presentations, portfolios and other forms of performance that demonstrate students' understanding and application of knowledge.

Despite the fact that the amount of work carried out in the field of development of theoretical and practical development of teaching pedagogical sciences in pedagogical higher education institutions is large enough, many issues related to the improvement of the working methodological system remain relevant. In the modern conditions where the processes of the educational system are changing, there are serious requirements for the inclusion and implementation of educational paradigms in the curriculum, that is, they are considered as a quality metacognitive tool that allows the formation of pedagogical professional competence of future teachers. . Currently, the methodology used for teaching pedagogical subjects is somewhat one-sided, that is, they are characterized by the fact that the main attention is allocated to the content component of the methodological system. Based on the content of what was said, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to develop the most effective methodology and to scientifically base it on the basis of the main requirements of the teaching of pedagogical subjects in pedagogical higher education institutions, the design method and cognitive approach to the teaching process. Such a conclusion is based on the fact that the success (quality) in teaching pedagogical subjects is in many cases interconnected, the relationship depends on a number of objective and subjective reasons, and depends on a whole complex of factors. will be strengthened. Subjective reasons include low level of readiness of students to plan and organize independent educational activities, low level of theoretical "training" and low level of motivation to the educational process. It is worth noting that many modern young people exhibit the so-called "clip" thinking, which is widespread and is more characteristic of the modern "network" generation of students. This is also reflected in the "diversity" that students experience in practical programming.

Currently, the effective methodology used in the preparation of students of pedagogical higher education institutions for the profession should be aimed at helping them acquire practical skills of pedagogical sciences, which often requires knowledge in the field of education, and the importance of developing thinking in an algorithmic form. should not be affected. It should not be overlooked that it is important to form a group of students who have a positive influence on their desire and are able to independently form additional and integrated knowledge acquisition skills, with motivational qualities. It is most optimal and appropriate to turn to the potential in the design approach, to the equipment that allows you to remove all the obstacles that destroy the plans of educational goals. The basis of the design method is built on the content of the cognitive approach, supplemented by a number of conceptual ideas from the entire cognitive science. We put forward the following idea, that is, if the design method is included in the construction of the educational process, the integration of the elements of the educational process will be activated, thereby creating favorable conditions for the development of students' thinking. Based on the content of what has been said, it can be noted that intellectual abilities that enable successful acquisition of knowledge within the framework of the program of pedagogical higher education institutions are involved as a content filling of the mentioned method.

Conclusion: Pedagogical science design methodology offers a dynamic and learner-centered approach to learning. By incorporating the principles of design thinking, educators can create engaging, personalized, and innovative learning experiences. This methodology provides empathy, encourages creative thinking, builds reflection and repetition, and focuses on achieving specific learning goals. Finally, adopting this methodology expands the teaching and learning process, allowing educators to design and deliver impactful learning experiences that empower students to succeed and thrive.

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